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Enhancing Interdisciplinary Skills in Engineering with the Cognitive Tools of Storytelling

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ABSTRACT

The studies carried out so far on how digital native students learn and think make researchers reevaluate the importance of the development of interdisciplinarity in higher education. In the case of engineering programs, the issue of strengthening interdisciplinarity is often hampered by the modality of logical-scientific thinking that predominates in all its courses and disciplines. The present work was based on the importance of the development of the narrative-artistic modality of thinking and the way to enhance creative experiences in the educational field. The cognitive tools of storytelling were adapted for the design of non-engineering, co-curricular activities related to fine arts and literature and were included in different programs of engineering. The methodology used was quantitative-experimental with a Solomon 4-group design and involved 183 engineering students. The measurement of results was carried out using different VALUE rubrics to evaluate the development of interdisciplinary skills and competencies of students, including critical thinking, creative thinking, and intercultural knowledge. The results showed that the selected cognitive tools of storytelling were highly useful for the development of interdisciplinary skills in engineering students.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The report, *Towards a Reskilling Revolution*, was released in January 2019 by the World Economic Forum, and it introduced a comparison of today’s skills with those demanded of future professionals to face the challenges of the so-called “Fourth Industrial Revolution.” Table 1 shows the skills expected to be trending or declining by 2022. Soft skills such as creativity, originality, and critical thinking are on the rise.

TABLE 1. World Economic Forum Report

Comparing skills demand		
	Today, 2018	Increasing, 2022
1	Analytical thinking and innovation	Analytical thinking and innovation
2	Complex problem-solving	Active learning and learning strategies
3	Critical thinking and analysis	Creativity, originality, and initiative
4	Active learning and learning strategies	Technology design and programming
5	Creativity, originality, and initiative	Critical thinking and analysis
6	Attention to detail, trustworthiness	Complex problem-solving
7	Emotional intelligence	Leadership and social influence
8	Reasoning, problem-solving and ideation	Emotional intelligence
9	Leadership and social influence	Reasoning, problem-solving and ideation
10	Coordination and time management	System analysis and evaluation

Source: *Towards the Reskilling Revolution report*

The Occupational Information Network (O * NET) defines *critical thinking* as the ability to use logic or reasoning to identify the strengths and weaknesses of alternative solutions, conclusions, or approaches to problems. Likewise, *creative thinking* is defined as the metacognitive process that allows not only complex problem solving but also promotes a high degree of innovation. In this sense, it is essential to strengthen these two soft skills in the training of future engineers, with the objective of enabling them to perform disruptive tasks successfully and to confront problems for which they have not learned solutions.

The importance of soft skills in engineering, especially critical thinking and creativity, has been studied for many years by academic researchers. However, it has not been until very recently (since today’s freshmen, the digital natives, belong almost 100% to *Generation Z*) that the need has been seen to introduce innovative, effective ways to develop critical thinking and creativity among the *Generation Z* students, considering their particular characteristics. The year 2015 was the watershed for reports on the necessity to include new cognitive and metacognitive tools for full development of soft skills that would be needed by *Generation Z* students, due to two fundamental causes: first, the strong consolidation of social networks meant an unanticipated difference in the way recent graduates see the world, think about private and public matters, and become aware of themselves; and second, the exponential development of technological platforms became accessible to them [1].

Some exciting studies referring to the use of Storytelling as a cognitive tool for enhancing soft skills while fostering student engagement can be highlighted:

Hiromi Nishioka proposed in 2016 the use of digital storytelling as a collaborative tool to develop the construction of knowledge through the exercise of coherent discourses and lexical enhancing. The strength of this study was the clear and in-depth formulation of the cognitive theories that underpin collaborative learning based on storytelling [2].

Artur Lugmayr introduced in 2017 the term, “Serious-Storytelling,” as a powerful coherent speech construction tool in the current era of media digitization. The strength of this study was the depth in the categorization of the components of storytelling, the definition of a solid framework for it, and the foundation with respect to theories of cognitive processes [3].

Amreen Mistry proposed in 2017 the storytelling technique to acquire conceptual information in an effective way, perform critical analyses of texts, and impact the emotional commitment of students. The strength of this study was the establishment of relationships between the didactic technique and the affective domain of learning along with the capacity for student commitment that it can generate [4].

Helmut Hlavacs proposed in 2018 the technique of storytelling to insert learning content in narrative discourses and counteract the tendency of Generation Z students to be distracted by technology. The strength of this study was that it presented a complete state of the art on the technique and based its methodology on different instruments such as observations, questionnaires, and interviews with students [5].

The weaknesses of some of the previous studies were that in some cases, there were no data collection or evaluation of results, and in other cases, there was a lack of evaluation instruments to measure the impact of content retention and emotional commitment.

Our project consisted of an interdisciplinary approach that incorporated those storytelling tools that effectively trigger the cognitive and metacognitive processes of learning in a mixed infusion/immersion environment [6] and had the objective of developing, in future engineers, the soft skills required by employers. This study also proposed the solution to the various pending problems mentioned above; it had the following characteristics: (i) the work was carried out using a methodology and instruments previously tested in different authors’ works [7]; (ii) the instruction was applied to a large sample of students in a quantitative experimental research design; and (iii) the impact and findings were evaluated with tools specially designed for the educational field [8].

2 GENERATION Z AND HIGHER EDUCATION

Although Generation Z differs in many ways from Generation Y, especially in regard to learning styles, it is currently considered that the methods associated with the strengthening of skills and competencies related to critical and creative thinking can be designed by taking advantage of the numerous studies and works carried out in the past twenty years [9]. Furthermore, Generation Z students arrive at college, having varying levels of cognitive development and abilities in creativity and criticism. In our work, we have especially considered the level of cognitive development of the students and have adapted the procedure design to the unique characteristics of Generation Z.

Texting is a prominent mode of communication that is widely popular among Generation Z. One in three digital native students reports sending over one hundred messages a day [1]. This fact presents new challenges in the sense that students have almost created their own language in texting. Shortening words and using abbreviations have been at the core of texting from the beginning. Emoji, or emotion icons, add another layer to the text messaging language in which students are fluent. They can, in fact, carry on an entire conversation with these tiny pictures alone. However, this “language” cannot be considered a real narrative of Serious-Storytelling. One way to enrich the lexical experience has always been the practice of reading and

writing. However, today's digital natives do their academic work by copying and pasting documents, relying on automatic word processors to correct spelling and even grammar, and using digital social platforms such as YouTube, Instagram, and Snapchat to "tell" stories. All these narrative habits weaken the force of their argumentations, hinder their vocabulary acquisition, and fail to contribute to the development of their critical and creative skills.

3 COGNITIVE THEORIES AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The present work, with a methodology and instruments specially adapted for engineering students of Generation Z, was based on two long-established cognitive theories. First, Jerome Bruner's *theory of cognitive functioning* was revised to strengthen the students' skills in criticism through the narrative-artistic modality. This theory deals with the ability of students to find meaning in works of art and to develop new technological products by converting imaginative concepts into a believable reality. Secondly, John Dewey's *theory of the development of the mind* was revisited to achieve a higher degree of commitment of the students by increasing their creative thinking skills. This theory deals with the need to create active learning experiences in all academic courses through the exercise of aesthetic activities and their assessments.

Jerome Bruner points out that there are two modalities of cognitive functioning of thought, and each of them offers characteristic ways of constructing reality and ordering experience: The *logical-scientific modality* tries to fulfill the ideal of a mathematical, formal system of description and explanation. It uses categorization or conceptualization and the operations by which the categories are established, represented, idealized, and related to each other in order to build a system. The *narrative-artistic modality*, on the other hand, looks for connections between two events and uses procedures to establish the likelihood, not the truth. This thinking modality is concerned with how we perceive meaning for experience and deals with human intentions and actions, the vicissitudes and consequences that mark its course, and the events of experience in time and space.

Until now, educational theories have tried to avoid incorporating the narrative-artistic modality in engineering programs so as not to lose the rigor of the search for empirical truth. However, during our research, we have found that attempts to ignore one of the modalities at the expense of the other inevitably lose the possibility of developing flexible critical thinking and creativity. Critical thinking and creativity do not occur automatically but are processes that depend not only on the cognitive effort but also on the metacognitive processing, which in turn depends on the developmental stage of the student. Because in the same classroom, students with different levels of cognitive development coexist, we considered two fundamental concepts derived from Vygotsky's work, *Scaffolding and Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD)*. The "scaffolding" refers to the observed fact that when a teacher interacts with students with the intention of teaching, they tend to adapt the degree of help to the level of competence they perceive in themselves. The ZPD is the gap between the real development level of the students and the level of potential development that could occur with the teacher's guidance or the support of the classmates.

4 SERIOUS-STORYTELLING

Serious-Storytelling conveys a perspective in serious application contexts and uses the narratives with a purpose beyond the entertainment. Given that stories are a fundamental component of human memory and the basis for the most fundamental

cognitive events, it is understandable that emotions and reflection are two of the fundamental aspects of storytelling. The addition of storytelling activities to the learning process creates a personal relationship between the instructor and the audience and is also a powerful tool to engage students and form emotional connections to the topics under study.

Storytelling is also an ideal cognitive tool to include in Vygotsky's approach because it is based on active and collaborative learning and is produced through the knowledge and previous experience of students. The process of storytelling can be considered *mimesis* -artistic imitation- or visualization of real-world happenings, in a way that an engaged audience interacts with the narrative flow of a story and perceives the narrative as an emotional experience, in Dewey's theory style. The essential components of storytelling can be divided into four elements:

- *Perspective*. It is a subjective point of view and includes story features such as cognition and emotion.
- *Narrative*. It is the actual content of the story and includes features such as mimesis and digenesis.
- *Interactivity*. It is the essential interaction between the speaker and the audience and includes features such as engagement and decision.
- *Medium*. It is the message and includes features such as content and forms.

With respect to the academic framework, it is essential to understand that serious stories can be entertaining and fun, but their primary purpose is knowledge and value creation for a serious context matter [10]. In the case of Serious-Storytelling, the four components must be understood in such a way that the following features are achieved:

- Provision of real-world understanding.
- Self-reflective and introspective context.
- Intrinsic motivation.
- Relation to a matter of importance, experience, knowledge, and understanding.
- Self-empowerment and personal advancement.

In storytelling systems for entertainment, the notion of story progression entails a progression of events in time and space. Clear examples of this are films based on mythology, very trendy today. In Serious-Storytelling systems, which are intended to be used as cognitive tools in the academic field, the notion of progression of a story is much more complex, and it can be said that it is an abstract artifact that makes the story progress, instead of the characters, events, or a cause-effect relationship.

5 METHODOLOGY

Participants. The participants were 183 undergraduate students in engineering programs. They joined the study voluntarily, and 116 of them underwent metacognitive instruction for five semesters (the experimental group), while 67 students remained untrained (the control group).

Instruments. Two different types of instruments were used in this study. The first type had vocabulary tests, with multiple-choice and true or false questions designed to establish the approximate lexicon of each student, compared to the Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA). Second, to assess how well students performed each outcome and considering that assessing the evidence for competencies like critical thinking and creativity typically involves subjective judgments

concerning products or behaviors, we also used a second type of instrument, which we adapted from an already-existing rubric, the VALUE Rubrics, which had been developed for the Essential Learning Outcomes of the Association of American Colleges and Universities (AAC&U) [8].

The instruments for the data collection and the group criteria were the following:

PreTest: Vocabulary tests regarding COCA.

Treatment: Dialogue seminars and online discussion boards.

PostTest: Vocabulary test regarding COCA and Value Rubrics by AAC&U.

EG-PreT-T: Experimental Group with PreTest and Treatment (60 students)

EG-T: Experimental Group without PreTest, only Treatment (56 students)

CG-PreT: Control Group with PreTest (33 students)

CG: Control Group without PreTest (34 students)

Procedure. The research methodology of the study was quantitative-experimental to establish a correlation between groups of variables. The independent variable was our experimental variable or treatment, and the dependent variable was our result or criterion, with which we achieved the effects observed in the study. The research hypothesis was that interdisciplinary incorporation of Serious-Storytelling-based activities for the development of critical thinking and creativity leads to the enhancement of the engineering students' intellectual engagement and intercultural knowledge. The methodological design is schematically illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Procedure design.

6 AN EXAMPLE OF STORYTELLING ACTIVITY

Title of the Series of Activities: *Narratives with and without words: from a photograph to the story and vice versa.*

The fifteen different storytelling activities carried out during our study were designed relying on existing scholarship in the field around the world, including experiences from North America, Latin America, Europe, and Asia. The activities were based on the successful initiative that the MuseWeb Foundation, *Be Here: Main Street*, carries out together with the Smithsonian Institution, which consists of traveling exhibitions that are taken to small towns in the United States. The program bases their project on the conviction that everyone has a story that is worth sharing. These rarely heard narratives capture a “story” of the small towns of the United States based on experience, knowledge, and memory instead of historical data and dates. In this way, the stories published offer people a personal and authentic vision of the traditions and culture of a community.

For the proper development of the activities in the Serious-Storytelling framework, the *Text-Photography Binomials* were selected in a way that allows observing whether students effectively develop creative thinking through the verification of compliance with four performance criteria that were included in the VALUE Rubric of Table 3; namely, a) Attentiveness towards different situations; b) Competencies acquisition (reflect, create, adapt or model); c) Perspective-taking and, d) Knowledge of cultural worldview frameworks.

Example of activity: *Mexican Binomial*

Learning Objectives. The activity allowed the students to know the work of Mexican writer Juan Rulfo and to write their own stories and anecdotes of their childhood and home cities using Rulfo's style.

Background of the work. Juan Rulfo was one of the great literary innovators of the twentieth century. His 1953 work, *The Plain in Flames*, is considered one of the foundational classics of magical realism. Lesser known are his poignant photographs of Mexico, which exhibit remarkable parallels to his prose; his photo book, *Juan Rulfo's Mexico*, contains 175 pictures mainly taken between 1945 and 1955. Rulfo extracts unique moments through his photographs; his images of desolate, abandoned buildings and landscapes are expressions of the loneliness and anguish experienced by the artists of his time.

Preliminary Activity (infusion-immersion approach). Students were asked to read the stories that are part of *The Plain in Flames*; also, a brief virtual tour was provided so that they would know more about the artistic and social concerns of the time and the country in which the author lived.

Divergent Thinking Activity. Students were asked to search the internet for information about the author and his photographic work. The photo book, *Juan Rulfo's Mexico*, was introduced to the students. A discussion session was held where the students established a personal relationship with some of the stories and some of the photographs. The group was divided into teams of 4 participants, and there was a role-play activity in which each member of the team was characterized as a friend or colleague of the author. The students recorded with their cell phones short interviews of the type that would be included in a documentary program about Rulfo and his photographic work.

Convergent Thinking Activity. Each student chose a landscape photograph that he/she would have taken in the hometown and then wrote a short story (using Rulfo's style) based on the picture. The students told these in a final session where each storyteller shared his/her life while projecting the chosen picture.

The *Mexican Binomial* was selected because the stories told present a vision of Mexican society - at that time, mostly rural - after two significant social conflicts, the Mexican Revolution and the *Guerra Cristera*.

Another activity was the *American Binomial*, comprised of the book, *The Grapes of Wrath* (1939), by John Steinbeck and the photographs of *An American Exodus: A Record of Human Erosion* (1939) by Dorothea Lange and Paul Taylor, where the stories presented the rural poverty of a country and the Depression-era exodus that brought thousands of migrants to California in search of farm work.

Observations. Evidence was taken in the classroom to analyze the interactions and processes between the speaker and the audience. The four components of the narrative technique (perspective, narrative, interactivity, and medium) along with the Serious-Storytelling features already discussed in previous sections were verified in each session to encode / decode contextual knowledge and the way in which the narrative could be a vehicle to trigger emotional and cognitive responses in the audience.

7 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In order to verify that the students of the experimental group and the control group had similar initial conditions of the lexicon, the results of the vocabulary PreTest in both groups were compared. The initial comparison between 183 students (116 students of the EG-PreT-T and 67 of the CG-PreT) where the PreTests were applied revealed no significant differences in their vocabulary background. However, the PostTest comparison of the vocabulary scores revealed that the EG-PreT-T group showed significantly higher improvement than the CG-PreT.

The PostTests on critical thinking, creative thinking and Intercultural Knowledge using AAC&U rubrics showed that the experimental group attained 66% improvement in comparison with the students of the control group in the upper “Capstone” level and a 25% decrement in the number of students who remained at the lowest “Benchmark” level of the rubric. These results are shown in Table 2. Additionally, an example of a rubric adapted from the AAC&U VALUE Rubrics is shown in Table 3.

TABLE 2. AAC&U Rubrics distribution for EG and CG

Groups	Value Rubrics			
	Capstone	Milestones		Benchmark
	4	3	2	1
EG	30 %	35 %	23 %	12 %
CG	18 %	31 %	35 %	16 %
	+ 66 %	+ 13 %	- 34 %	- 25 %

Findings. The convergent stage of the activity present in the technique of Serious-Storytelling is the one that allows the assessment of the different performance criteria of the rubric; they were chosen based on the employers' requirements. It is noteworthy that it would not have been possible to apply a VALUE Rubric or obtain a correlation between the results of the PreTest and the PostTest if the activity had been limited only to entertainment storytelling.

Discussion on the creative thinking assessment: The rubrics were used with the intention of evaluating and discussing learning related to the students' interdisciplinary skills, not the grading. These rubrics allowed positioning the learning within a basic framework of expectations [10].

Discussion on the inclusion of Serious-Storytelling in engineering courses: The incorporation of artistic activities, such as those presented in this study, to develop soft

skills in engineering courses is a proposal of educational innovation in response to compliance with the requirements of employers and accreditation agencies. This concept responds to the growing need to achieve integrated thinking in engineers. It is suggested that the incorporation of storytelling activities into the curricular courses be carried out by trained instructors and follow a sequential taxonomy of the type: creating, inventing, innovating, engineering, and controlling [11]. It is precisely in the first two stages of the process (creating and inventing) where the development of artistic activities could help to free the modality of narrative-artistic thinking explained in previous sections.

TABLE 3. Example of the Rubric used as PostTest. (*This rubric was created using the Association of American Colleges and Universities (AAC&U) VALUE Rubrics*) [8].

	Capstone 4	Milestones		Benchmark 1
		3	2	
Attentiveness towards different situations	Interprets intercultural experience from the perspectives of self and more than one worldview and demonstrates the ability to act in a supportive manner that recognizes the feelings of another cultural group.	Recognizes intellectual and emotional dimensions of more than one worldview and sometimes uses more than one worldview in interactions.	Identifies components of other cultural perspectives but responds in all situations with own worldview.	Views the experience of others but does so through their own cultural worldview.
Acquiring competencies	Reflect: Evaluates creative process and product using domain-appropriate criteria.	Create: Creates an entirely new object, solution or idea that is appropriate to the domain.	Adapt: Successfully adapts an appropriate exemplar to his/her own specifications.	Model: Successfully reproduces an appropriate exemplar.
Perspective-taking	Evaluates and applies diverse perspectives to complex subjects within natural and human systems in the face of multiple and even conflicting cultural positions.	Synthesizes other perspectives (such as cultural, disciplinary, and ethical) when investigating subjects within natural and human systems.	Identifies and explains multiple perspectives (such as cultural, disciplinary, and ethical) when exploring subjects within natural and human systems.	Identifies multiple perspectives while maintaining a value preference for their own cultural positioning.
Knowledge of cultural worldview frameworks	Demonstrates sophisticated understanding of the complexity of elements important to members of another culture in relation to its history, values, or beliefs.	Demonstrates adequate understanding of the complexity of elements important to members of another culture in relation to its history, values, or beliefs.	Demonstrates partial understanding of the complexity of elements important to members of another culture in relation to its history, values, or beliefs.	Demonstrates surface understanding of the complexity of elements important to members of another culture in relation to its history, values, or beliefs.

8. Conclusions

The 21st-century engineers must be creative and critical enough to build values and judgments and even solve ill-defined problems to understand and remember conceptual information. The results of our study showed that Serious-Storytelling could be an effective cognitive tool to enhance specific dispositions of particular soft skills, such as perspective-taking (critical thinking) and acquiring competencies (creative thinking), that foster the abilities and dispositions of temperament that are required by employers. Additionally, we could verify that our method propitiated the development of specific personal attitudes necessary for the future engineers of Generation Z: attentiveness towards different situations (empathy) and knowledge of global cultural frameworks (intercultural competence).

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